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Exploring Women's Struggles and the Impact of Patriarchy in the Literary Works of Urvashi Butalia

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Abstract:

Urvashi Butalia, a prominent feminist author and publisher, examines the intersection of patriarchal society and women's movements. Feminism, evolving from its Latin roots meaning "woman," now represents a global movement for women's rights and equality. Feminist theory argues that women have been historically marginalized in male-dominated societies—a theme central to Butalia's work. This study critically analyzes her influential book, "The Other Side of Silence: Voices from the Partition of India," which documents the traumatic experiences of women during the 1947 Partition through oral histories and personal narratives. Butalia uncovers silenced voices, highlighting the gendered aspects of historical events often ignored in mainstream historiography. The research also explores postcolonial feminism, which critiques colonial ideologies and emphasizes non-Western knowledge in challenging imperialist narratives. Beyond her writings, Butalia co-founded India's first feminist publishing house, Kali for Women, in 1984, and later Zubaan Books. The study concludes that Butalia's

work not only counters official histories but also empowers women to reclaim their narratives and assert their identities in a patriarchal society.

Keywords: Urvashi Butalia, Patriarchal Society, Woman, Partition, Feminist.

Introduction:

The Latin word "Femina," meaning "woman," is the origin of the English word "feminism," which was first used to describe the movement for women's rights and equality. Being feminine or womanly is the definition of "feminism" according to the Oxford English Dictionary. The word "feminism" is defined by Webster's Dictionary as the belief that women should have the same political rights as men. Conservative commentator Toril Moi argues, "The words 'feminist' or 'feminism' are political labels indicating support for the aims of the new Woman's Movement which emerged in the late 1960s." Similarly, Simone de Beauvoir claims that the balanced usage of masculine and feminine is just an aesthetic choice in legal documents. From one individual to another, the phrase "feminism" might mean different things. "A way of life in which the woman is free of the dependence syndrome" is how Chaman Nahal describes feminism in his essay "*Feminism in English Fiction*." Whether it's a spouse, a parent, a neighborhood, a church, or a race, there's a reliance syndrome. My conception of feminism comes to fruition when women overcome the dependency mentality and live independently.

Feminist theory is based on the premise that women have always been second-class citizens in societies and in Western intellectual traditions that males have ruled. All culture's annals reveal that women have always been second-class citizens, unable to reassert their individuality until they go back into the past, learn from it, and then build it from the ground up. For women to delve into their own identity, they must first establish who they are through the traditionally male-dominated norms and assumptions that have been handed down through the years. Because of these ideas, a dominating system has emerged, with female subjects socialized to adopt the system's principles. Men degrade and abuse the physical cosmos in the same way they degrade and exploit women, turning them into submissive creatures and altruistic objects. Thus, males have achieved tremendous power to manipulate their domination over women and nature in all three of these domains: historical traces, philosophical or epistemic heritage, and ecological inhaling. To rephrase, women are compelled to depend on and draw their very life from males due to their historical insignificance.

For the most part, the philosophical and epistemological framework has treated women as if they were either sexual objects whose desires fluctuate between lust and jealousy or nonexistent creatures. Since women have long been associated with the calming, soothing, and ir-resistive qualities of nature-loving, caring, clay, earth, moon, reproduction, and nurturing—the third kind of exploitation relates to the exploitation of nature. By demonstrating opposition to and protest against male-coded norms of behavior, feminist theorists cast doubt on these assumptions. To re-establish the feminist literary canon, they use theoretical and philosophical frameworks to base their counterarguments and engage in historical revisionism. Feminist literary theory, then, is a philosophical and theoretical development of feminism that seeks to understand the literary legacy of women and the factors that contribute to their subordinate positions. They went through several steps to develop their own distinct identity while challenging phallogocentric ideas. They were able to finally achieve what had been denied to them for centuries because of these developmental phases. This suggests that there have been three distinct periods in the development of the contemporary Western feminist movement.

Postcolonialism is a critical framework that has evolved to see colonialism as an ideology that may be effectively challenged by non-Western knowledge traditions. Edward Said, a scholar of colonial discourse, laid the groundwork for post-colonial theory with his publications, most notably *Orientalism* (1978). Said examined the nineteenth-century European representation of the numerous cultures it encountered during imperial expansion and said that the West created these non-Western civilizations to serve as an "Other" to its norms. Scholars and travelers painted a negative picture of these foreign civilizations, highlighting how different they were from Britain. So, according to Said, the civilized, hardworking Britons saw other peoples as barbarous, slobs, uncivilized, and sluggish. Both the colonized (in places like India and Africa) and the colonizers (in Britain and France, for example) during the nineteenth century sought to understand and explain the long-lasting effects of European imperialism. In response to some globalizing trends in Said's work, postcolonial theory has emerged in the last decade. So, postcolonialism has emerged to provide a fresh and critical take on colonialism. Additionally, it has ignited significant debates. The whole integrity of the body of knowledge derived from the Enlightenment's heritage of reason and science is called into question. Since postcolonial languages have been so diverse, they may as well be incomprehensible.

A patriarchal society and the subordination of women:

The patriarchal structure has always been there. Its presence persists in the present era despite the passage of time. This indicates that patriarchal societies are not the only ones in which women continue to be subordinated. The reason is, that males are more likely to hold positions of power in patriarchal societies. The patriarchal social order gives males special privileges. As stated by Pilcher and Whelehan (Whelehan 93), patriarchy may be defined as the practice of having a man serve as the leader of any social unit, whether it is a family, tribe, or community. What this means is that males are seen as the natural leaders of their families and communities under patriarchal systems. "Patriarchy in its wider definition means the manifestation and institutionalization of male dominance over women and children in the family and the extension of male dominance over women in society in general," Lerner (Lerner 239) explains, in keeping with this idea. By reading the definition, the author understands that patriarchy is a social structure in which males (or fathers) have the power to direct and control their family members (including spouses, younger men, children, and domestic staff). Additionally, the system recognizes males as having the inherent authority to govern the community, which includes both men and women in particular.

Patriarchal households often have clear roles for men and women. The public realm is associated with males and the home sphere with women. It is reasonable to expect men to work outside the home as they provide for their families. The traditional role of women is that of homemaker and mother. Men still hold the majority of positions in these fields, however. When it comes to the household's finances, males have a prominent role, particularly as breadwinners. Women will not have access to their funds unless they work for a pay. Therefore, to meet their basic needs, women must rely on males who are economically superior to them. In addition, males are also entitled to lead and make decisions inside the home, including those that concern the present and the future of the family members. For his daughter's future spouse, a parent may, for instance, arrange a marriage. As a result of the patriarchal system's tendency to dominate women, women in it will have little flexibility to pursue their interests. Men, being social and familial beings, may also govern and be dominated by other men. So, it's plausible that males might feel subjugated by men.

Exploring Gender and History: The Impact of Urvashi Butalia's Work:

Feminist author, publisher, and activist Urvashi Butalia was born in 1952 in India. Among her many accomplishments, she is most recognized for her contributions to the Indian women's movement and the publications of books like *Speaking Peace: Women's Voices from*

Kashmir and The Other Side of Silence: Voices from and the Partition of India. In 1984, she and Ritu Menon co-founded the first feminist publishing firm in India, Kali for Women. Zubaan Books, a division of Kali for Women, was established by her in 2003. For their contributions to literature and education, Butalia and Menon shared India's fourth highest civilian honor, the Padma Shri, in 2011.

Urvashi Butalia co-founded the first feminist publishing company in India, Kali for Women, founded in 1984. After Kali closed its doors in 2003, she took over as director of Zubaan, another feminist imprint. She has been active in India's women's movement for a long time, and now she works as a freelance researcher and writer, publishing extensively on gender-related topics. She has been honored with many prestigious titles, such as the Padmashri, the Goethe Medal, the Nikkei Asia Award for Culture, and the French Chevalier des Lettres et des Artes.

Ritu Menon, Urvashi Butalia, and Kali for Women (1992). *In Other Words: New Writing by Indian Women*. Ritu Menon and Urvashi Butalia (1995). *Making a Difference: Feminist Publishing in the South*. Urvashi Butalia and Tanika Sarkar (1995). *Women and the Hindu Right: A Collection of Essays*. Urvashi Butalia and Tanika Sarkar (1995). *Women and Right-Wing Movements: Indian Experiences*. Butalia Urvashi (1998). *The Other Side of Silence: Voices from the Partition of India*. Butalia Urvashi (2002). *Speaking Peace: Women's Voices from Kashmir*. Butalia, Urvashi, ed. (2006). *Inner Line: The Zubaan Book of Stories by Indian Women*.

The Other Side of Silence: Voices from The Partition of India by Urvashi Butalia:

Since the beginning of time, there has been violence against women. The topic of violence against women and the age-old taboo of seeing women in a subordinate role both continue today. Women have a subordinate position in patriarchal societies. Their wants, desires, talents, beliefs, and opinions are mostly irrelevant. Consequently, women have made very little headway even after gaining independence. The story of women's "progress" is portrayed as a sluggish and hardly noticeable uphill battle, as pointed out by Rajeswari Sunder Rajan. A territorial split occurred as a result of India's independence. The atrocities of the Holocaust and the division are vividly shown in Chaman Nahal's *Azadi*. One of the bloodiest chapters in human history occurred in 1947 when India was partitioned. Victims and witnesses on both sides of the border were shaken to the core. In *South Asian Partition Fiction in English:*

From Khushwant Singh to Amitav Ghosh, Rituparna Roy notes that 'the experiences of women at the period of partition' were overlooked in both elite historiography and subaltern history. 'Women were sacrificed, abducted, or reclaimed in a war which gave importance to society and hierarchy at the price of individual rights,' said one feminist author in the 1990s, when the feminist movement was at its height (Roy 19). Through the stories told to her by women, in particular, Urvashi Butalia reveals the many facets of the partition's history in *The Other Side of Silence*. She searches the divider for females. Talking to those who were there during the division evokes a flood of memories, particularly from women. *Borders & Boundaries* features Ritu Menon and Kamala Bhasin: *Victims of India's Split* is chronicled in *Women in India's Split*. They, too, depend on first-hand accounts to delve into the nuances of women's lives during the division, much like Butalia. The narrative of displacement, victimization, and the horrific breaking of women's bodies and souls is carefully shown in Butalia. Politics and history inevitably mold human life, but the division almost eradicated women from history. The brutality was so severe that it rendered them speechless. They were rendered speechless and handled with contempt. Their feeling of citizenship and belonging was always up for debate. Thus, the history of the split is still hard to ignore.

Acts of Violence Against Women During the Partition: A Historical Examination:

According to Butalia's study, it has been shown that sexual violence was rampant during Partition. Approximately 100,000 women were subjected to various forms of abuse, including abduction, rape, forced marriage, and prostitution. The seventh chapter of Butalia Bapsi Sidhwa's *Cracking India*, similar to Urvashi Butalia's *The Other Side of Silence*, provides a glimpse into the complicated positionality of rape during partition via its depiction of the event. Forced marriage was a reality for women during the partition. Lots of people were taken. The abductors and rapists would often compel the ladies to marry them. They were compelled to marry inside their church and were coerced into becoming believers. Also, addressed in this homily was the fate of the kidnapped ladies who had surrendered so readily to the 'other's' faith. However, according to Butalia, *Pinjar*, by Amrita Pritam, is set against the background of division and details the rejection that Puro feels after being abducted and raped (Butalia 187). Pregnant women were a major issue for society during the division. The practice of forced abortion was instituted as a response to this issue. The social workers' confirmation of the practice of sending pregnant women to designated locations for either having children (who were subsequently given for adoption) or for mass abortions (*safaya*) solidified the practice.

Even though abortion was technically prohibited at the time, the state-funded mass abortions using a designated fund. (Butalia 161) Rape often targeted women because of their perceived weakness. Under the pretense of martyrdom and honor murders, the brutality even emanated from within the same family and community. "On both sides of the border at Partition, nearly 75,000 women had been raped and abducted," she reported (Butalia 132). In certain cases, families did not accept raped women back. They were coerced into prostitution or remained with the abuser, even converting to their faith. The opposing side committed sexual assaults on women, raped them, and eventually murdered them.

For fear of dishonoring themselves in the eyes of those of other faiths, relatives also murdered women. A little town was the setting for the event. Throughout Pakistan, the figure of Thoa Khalsa has become legendary. In response to concerns that Muslims could assault, some 90 Sikh women hurried into the hamlet. A survivor who managed to stay alive while it filled up later recounts the experience. Having almost avoided an honorable demise, her words had an air of sorrow. *Tamas*, written by Bhisham Sahni, also recounts a similar event. While the primary focus of *Tamas* is the graphic depiction of communal violence, the film also addresses the tragic situation of the Sikh woman who committed suicide by jumping into the well to avoid being molested. As a result, women were forcibly separated from their children and families. Because of the difficulty of their journeys, women endured much hardship. Families, friends, and children had to be left behind by the women. Destruction and death were all over the place. There was always the terrifying possibility of becoming a victim of sexual assault. Butalia tells the tale of Shehnaj, whose real name was Harbhajan Kaur. Afzal Khan chose her, and they were married. They had five children together. They would not release her when she returned to India to see them. The children, however, may be accepted, but the spouse, may not. At long last, the father takes his five children back to Pakistan, where he marries again and takes care of them. The Sikh who had a son from Harbhajan's previous marriage married Harbhajan to another woman. Harbhajan brings up this kid. After living in the United States for half a century, this stepson discovers his mother's untold tale and, with the help of the media, brings her to Pakistan. Shehnaj wants to remain in Pakistan so she may be with the kids. Abduction, marital rape, religious conversion, kid separation, and a spectacular union (which did not happen to everyone) are all parts of this narrative.

Urvashi Butalia and the Emergence of India's Feminist Press: A History of Women in Press:

The women's movement in India likely had its most exciting and motivating period in the early 1980s, when it was showing signs of hopeful new advances and successes. The memory of the 1984 London International Feminist Book Fair (IFBF) fills Ritu Menon with an overwhelming sense of longing. A global gathering of feminist writers and publishers came together to get to know one another and form stronger bonds:

At Covent Garden, everyone could witness the remarkable energy and potential of the worldwide women's movements. Authors, publishers, and activists such as Alice Walker, Toni Cade Bambara, Buchi Emecheta, Fatima Mernissi, Nawal el Saadawi, Alifa Rifat, Barbara Smith, Ellen Kuzwayo, Gert Brandenberg, Suniti Namjoshi, and Madhu Kishwar were there, offering the knowledge and perspective that would change the world. (*Dismalting* 289)

While Women's Studies emerged as a new academic field on the global stage, the feminist press was a doomed endeavor supported only by the selfless passion and limited resources of its founders. The conservative media, which feminists call the "malestream," thought this was too niche and too dangerous to publish financially. Books on women's problems or written from a feminist point of view would go unpublished by a profit-driven mainstream publisher. Even while "Feminist publishing . . . came about as a consequence of the women's movement, and in solidarity with it," says Menon, "Resistance was its *raison d'etre*" (Menon 291).

The majority of feminist authors have also been campaigners, penning part-time work to influence lawmakers and the general public. The feminist press may have flourished in the mid-1980s. The women's movement in India received tremendous support from the publishing firm Kali for Women, which Urvashi Butalia and Ritu Menon co-founded. There was a shift in preference towards local concerns and indigenous talent as a consequence of the weakening of the Indian rupee compared to the dollar and the pound, and an increase in indigenous publishing firms. According to what Butalia says in her piece,

Despite being a huge and relatively steady market for imported books, the Indian market started to shift somewhat as the value of the rupee dropped, making it more costly to import books from countries like the US and UK. Some publishers considered the prospect of

establishing a local publishing sector as market opposition to imported books' high pricing started to take shape... (Other Tongues 108)

Taking advantage of these advantageous market circumstances, feminist literature set out to solidify its position. Kali for Women was a tiny, independent press that focused on releasing materials on difficulties faced by Indian women. As Butalia said it once more:

We set out to do a few things when we founded Kali for Women, the first feminist publishing firm in India, many years ago. Publications of the period failed to portray the vibrant women's movement taking place inside India, even though the movement itself was rather powerful. As feminists and publishers, we felt obligated to investigate the possibility of a market for books written and published by women and to fill it with their works. The books we published were based on research in the social sciences and the humanities, and they may add to what is already known about women in the field. (Other Tongues 111)

Conclusion:

We can say that Feminism is an ideology that is still in its infancy; it dates back to the late 18th century at the latest. When compared to other ideologies, feminism stands out because it essentially disregards or assumes the significance of many of the issues addressed by other philosophies. Feminist theory has evolved from an unorganized and disorganized system of resistance against phallographic thought and practice into a robust area of academic research. Butalia suggests a counter-memory that finds its way into official history by drawing on the recollections of kidnapped women. With this structure in place, women can take charge of their narratives by sharing them via their unique voices. In her work on *The Other Side of Silence*, Butalia has also made efforts to fill up gaps in historical knowledge. It acknowledges that people are responsible for the traumas that have happened in the past and places their experiences into discursive frameworks to demonstrate how relevant they are now.

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